

ISSUES OF TRANSLATION OF UZBEK PROSE WORKS INTO A FOREIGN LANGUAGE (BASED ON THE WORK “SUCH IS LIFE” BY UTKIR KHOSHIMOV)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13168511>

Abstract. *Translation of samples of Uzbek prose works into foreign languages plays an important role in the development of intercultural dialogue and the global expansion of Uzbek literature. Therefore, in the process of turning selected works into a foreign language, a great methodological skill and experience is required from linguists and translators.*

Keywords: *translation, interpretation, artistic translation, prose.*

Today, translators have great difficulties in reflecting the linguistic terms, cultural references and methodological features inherent in Uzbek prose. In our scientific work aimed at these methods of comparative analysis, it is aimed at solving similar linguistic problems, methodically providing theoretical guidance and illuminating them through practical analysis. When translating different texts into different languages, it is important to highlight cultural information through translation strategies and find their equivalents in another language.

According to Gofurov and a group of other scholars, translation is a type of literary creation that consists of recreating linguistic units in a new language, from documents, texts, manuscripts, works of art, to proverbs and sayings in a particular language. Translation is considered one of the most important manifestations of interethnic communication. As early as the time of the oldest communities, the process of translation arose due to the need for interaction between people, communication, and until today this area has become polished throughout its development and has time to gain its place and importance in various aspects of our life. The concept of “translation” refers to the process of turning a certain text or work from one language to another, as well as a finished translation work.

Translation and interpretation are considered one of the areas of ancient creative activity that has been developing in the history and culture of the peoples of the world for many centuries. The descendants of mankind, who have been living in different corners and regions of the world for several thousand years, have also manifested their creativity, interests, hobbies, opportunities through translation. Looking at the translation work carried out to this day, one can list the translation centers of 8th-9th centuries by arab linguists and translators, in the cities of Kufa, Baghdad and Damascus, and in the 12th-14th centuries-prosperous Andalusian translation centers in Toledo, Bologna, Petersburg translation centers led by Peter I at the beginning of the 18th century.

Since translation has long been a means of communication between peoples and nations or a bridge of cultural exchange, significant work has been carried out on translatability, even in the immediate East. The translation of hundreds of important, significant books written by Persian, Indian scholars and ADIBS that emerged during the Renaissance, the great cultural boom, as well as the translation of encyclopedian scholar Abu Rayhon Beruni, testifies to the flourishing of work on language, culture and translation in the countries of the East. Our esteemed erudite scholar Abu Rayhon Beruni's translation of four verses from Persian into Arabic, about twenty scientific books from Arabic to Hindi and Hindi to Arabic is a vivid example of the need for translation even then.

MAIN PART.

The first translations of the prose works of Uzbek literature into English are naturally associated with the name of Alisher Navoi. The epic “Lison ut-tyre” was translated into English by Ye. Fitzgerald and published in Boston, United States in 1988. The prose account of this work was written by the translator Harry Dick, the Uzbek translator N.Qambarov was translated into English in collaboration. The treatise discussion “Muhokamat ul-lug‘atayn ” was printed in the US in 1966 as a book in the translation of Robert Deveruks, while the author's epic “Sab'ai sayyor” was translated by the American professor V. Firman. In 1988, Alisher Navoi's proverbs were published in the Latin alphabet in an English translation by Margaret Betlin by the Uzbek society “Homeland”.

In addition, in the world-wide distribution of Uzbek literature, the work “Baburnoma”, created by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, also deserves special mention. Dilbarkhan Akhmedova, a graduate student at the University of Washington, made a detailed reference to English translations of this rare work in a multi-reference article entitled “The Book in English”, published in the August 15, 2018 edition of “literature and art of Uzbekistan”. The young researcher writes that the first translation and publication of the “Boburnoma ” into English was in 1826, which was published by the English Orientalists J.With Leiden and Erskines. The second translation of the work is associated with the name of the English scientist Annetta Beveridge. In the 1900s, the British Orientalist scholar H.Beverij wins a copy of the “Boburnoma” in Hyderabad and announces it in facsimile form in London in 1905. His wife, Annetta Beverijchonim, worked long to translate from this facsimile copy into English.

Also, another young nobleman, Mrs. Ilza Sirtautas, on the translation of the treasures of Uzbek literature into English, prepared several works in Uzbek with his students for publication in English at a later time under his leadership. For example, Chulpan's “Tulip in the belly”, G.Ghulam's "My bastard child", A.Qahhor's "Pomegranate”, “Patient”, Mirkarim Osim's “Shiroq”, Said Ahmad's “Horse”, “Mirage”, Saida Zunnunova's "Hands", O.Umarbekov's “The clock”, “Dutar”, Otkir Hoshimov's “Picture”, were translated into English and presented to readers. In the 19th and 21st centuries, a look at the work of translation carried out in Europe, great scholars have contributed to the development of translation theory during this period. Including P.Newmark, J.Catford, Y.Nayda, A.Daff, A.Malley, D.Schweitzer, L.B.Barkhudarov, Y.N.Komissarov, A.Y.Fyodorov, D.Robinson, M.Shakhin, Levitskaya, Fitterman, we can cite such linguistic scientists, as examples. A number of prose and literary works by European scholars have also been translated into Uzbek and delivered to readers. For example, in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Arthur Conan Doyle's “Tales of Sherlock Holmes” and Daniel Defoe's “Robinson Crusoe” were masterfully translated into Uzbek.

In the following decades, Uzbek readers began to read a number of works of world literature figures in Uzbek. In particular, Erkin Vohidov translated the famous German scientist Goethe's “Faust” into Uzbek. A.Oripov translated Dante's “Divine Comedy”, Kadir Mirmuhammedov translated Homer's “Odyssey” into Uzbek.

Juan Luis Vieves, a 15th-century Spanish scholar, humanist, also contributed to translation. In 1631, in his “specimens and translations”, he makes the following remarks on the principles and methods of translation: *“Translation is the preservation of the originality of meaning when one word is being transformed from one language to another. In some translations, you can see only the meaning, and in others only the phrase and the correct pronunciation. When someone wants to turn the speeches of Demosthenes or Marcus Tullius or, if not, the poems of Homer and Vergilius into another language, he should initially focus on the structure of the main text and speech. If he translated, he must have realized the great difference between languages, if he did not do it before, no language will notice that the methodological features and the structure of speech of another*

language are not rich enough to match each other, and even in the oldest languages, the situation is such."

Juan Luis Vieves argues that the meaning that the translated texts represent must be freely translated, and that in such cases the translator can drop a thought or use the word he needs.

In addition, a number of European scientists and thinkers have given their own various ideas on translation. Due to the different differences between languages, in a time when there were also different problems and difficulties associated with the translation process, many philosophers, thinkers of the Eastern renaissance in the 9th and 12th centuries were engaged in these problems, such as Al-Khwarizmi, Abu Rayhon Beruniy, Al-Farghani, Abu Nasr Farabi, Mahmud Koshgari, Mahmud Zamakhshari, Yusuf Khos Hajib. Therefore, it is worth noting the merits of the great thinker Alisher Navoi in the formation and development of interpreting as a scientific science.

The first work on the creation and development of translation works in our country begins with Qutb Khorezmi's translation of Nizami Ganjavi's epic "Khusrav and Shirin" into Uzbek in the 1330s-1340s. In the 19th and 20th centuries, translation was further developed. Artists such as Chulpan, Ghafur Ghulam, Oybek, Abdullah Qahhor, Mirtemir, Maqsud Shaykhzoda, Mirzakalon Ismaili, Asqad Mukhtar, Erkin Wahidov, Abdullah Oripov, Muhammad Ali made important contributions to Uzbek translation. Also, in the field of artistic translation, M.Osim, N.Alimuhamedov, Sh.Shomuhamedov, K.Kahhorova, O.Sharopov, Sh.Tolipov, V.Ro ' zimatov, Q.Mirmuhamedov, A.Rashidov, M.Hakimov, I.Gafurov, M.Mirzohidov, G'. Torabekov and others are known as professional translators. Juan Luis Vieves argues that the meaning that the translated texts represent must be freely translated, and that in such cases the translator can drop a thought or use the word he needs.

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Great progress has also been made in the translation of scientific and technical, socio-political literature in the Uzbek language. In this case, the contribution of such translators as Z.Tincherova R.Abdurahmanov, V.Rahimov, Sh.Shomahmudov, is significant . In our country, a number of level work has been carried out in the field of translation, and a number of translation schools have been founded. In particular, the early research of professor Gaibulla Salomov began the years when he was still studying at Samarkand State University. His brochures such as "Translation of proverbs, materials and idioms", "lexical-phraseological issues of artistic translation", "translation of proverbs from Russian into Uzbek " were published. Shortly thereafter,

his monograph” language and translation “was printed in the publishing house” fan. The famous translator, in addition to work on translation in these years, also carried out the work of writing and lexicography, also wrote scientific works on the same field. Monographs and textbooks entitled” translator skills“,” bridges of friendship“,” problems of artistic translation and literary editing“,” translation concerns“,” problems of literary tradition and artistic translation“,” introduction to translation theory“,” fundamentals of translation theory ” were published.

Today, in modern Uzbek translation of the 21st century, many young and talented translators and linguists carry out certain work in the direction of translation. Among them, Khurshid Davran, Muhammad Ali, Ibrahim Ghafurov, Ququrkhan Musayev, Abduzukur Abduazizov, Najmiddin Komilov, Ibrahim Ghafurov, Begoyim Kholbekova are listed.

It is known that when translating works into another language, there are several main dimensions at the heart of comparative analysis. First, translation strategies vary widely among translators. Most translators view word-for-word translation into the original Uzbek text optimally, and in this context they attempt to preserve the linguistic structure of the text as well as its lexical meaningfulness. Others aim to deliver to the reader in a way that resonates the basic meaning and culturally the characters of the chosen text. It is these approaches in the field of translation that can have a good effect on how translated texts or works are perceived and understood by other peoples and nations. From such points of view, it is worth noting that when translating works of art, a great knowledge and ingenuity or, if not, thoughtful thought are required from the translator. As the translator focuses on the translation of a text, he will have the ability to reflect both thoughts and views in his own brain in the translation of that text, taking into account first of all the lexical-grammatical elements in that text, as well as aspects of lingucultural and historians.

So about the academic fame of the translation of the work of art we can cite the following opinion of Sirojiddinov: *“the meaning of the concept of translation is very broad. From one language to another, fiction: poetry, dramatic and prose works, scientific and popular books on various fields of Science, documents of diplomacy, you will say, official documents, articles of political figures and speeches of speakers, newspaper materials, conversations of people who speak other languages, need the service of “tilmoch” are translated, motion pictures are turned”. Translation is a type of literary creation that consists of recreating text in one language in another. Translation is the most important view of interethnic communication. Depending on the nature of the original and reconstructed text, artistic translation, scientific translation and other types are distinguished”.*

Today, there are various methods of translating texts and documents related to the work of art and other types of translation by translators, which are used in the translation process. Translation types are divided into two types according to their form: written translation and oral translation.

Written translation includes translations of fiction, science and other fields. Oral translation, on the other hand, is divided into synchronous and sequential translation. In addition to translation types, translation methods are also considered very important. There are several types of translation methods. These include:

Adequate translation - (Russian adequate lot. in Uzbek, equalization is an equivalent, fully consistent, exactly similar translation to each other (meaning that the translation corresponds to the original). That is, in this type of translation, a translation that fully reflects the original, in accordance with it and equates with it is called an adequate translation. For example, this passage from the story “the affairs of the world” by acute Hoshimov *“Qarang, oyi, yetti og‘ayni orasidagi eng yorug‘ yulduz – meniki”* the sentence can be translated in English as follows: *“Look, Mum among seven brothers the lightest star is – mine”*, that is, the meaning of all the components that

make up this sentence is proportional to each other in terms of completeness in both languages. When the work was translated into English by A.Roziyev and Mark Reese, the sentence was translated as follows: “*Look, mama, the brightest star among its Big Dipper-all mine*”. So this type of translation is called adequate, that is, absolutely proportional translation.

Adaptation translation - (lot. adaptatio; relief, simplification) is a simplified translation of a work or other text in origin, mainly by emphasizing plot lines and avoiding recognition of its meaning and stylistic aspects. In this type of translation, the main focus is on the intended meaning, and in a simple, uncomplicated case, the reader is delivered the original meaning of the text.

Text in Uzbek: *Bolaligimni eslasam iliq yoz kechalari ko‘z oldimga keladi.*

Text in English:

When I remember my childhood, these images from the warm summer evenings appear before me.

In all periods, the colorful types and methods associated with translation are identified and used in the translation process. Currently, the following types of translation are distinguished:

1. Sequential translation.
2. Visual translation.
3. Synchronous translation.

Sequential translation in this type of translation, after giving oral information in one language, it is translated into another language.

Once the information in one language is heard, the translator listens to the speaker's thoughts and records the general information needed and the information given is delivered in a sequential manner.

Visual translation. Visual translation is said to translate and read a text or work of art written in the same language into another language.

Some translators consider the written form of that speech before making a visual translation. It is necessary to see and translate the text in the place reserved for translation, not to be heard like reading a written text, but like oral speech.

In synchronous translation, the translator sits in a designated place for translation and listens to the speaker through the earphone. Then he translates through the microphone while listening. Delegates in the conference room listen to the main language through headphones. Synchronous translation can also be performed through gestures (for deaf and dumb). Translated from spoken language into sign language. Sign interpreters do not sit in places designated for them, they stand in a conference room where they can see the speaker and see other participants.

Cultural translation of the text of a work of art is also the main process of translation. In Uzbek literature, in many cases, cultural views, Customs and historical processes in the Uzbek language can be unfamiliar to representatives of another nationality. In such cases, what is required of translators is to carefully monitor the nuances calculated by cultural signs and reflect them in the translation process. This provides sufficient context without increasing or simplifying the richness of the text. In the English edition of the story “the affairs of the world” by O‘tkir Hoshimov, sentences related to Uzbek customs and realities are translated as follows:

Text in Uzbek

– Esiz bir bechoraning joni uzildi-ya...Yuragim shuv etib onamning pinjiga kirardim.
Ishqilib, boshqa yulduz uchmasin!

Text in English:

“Alas...a poor soul has left us.” “My heart would catch in my throat, and I would hold myself to my mother’s bosom. *And thus, in that manner, the stars would case their falling from the heavens!* ”

It is known that there is an opinion from our ancestors that “if a star flies in the sky, someone's soul will be cut off on Earth.” Since this concept is not found in other nations and in the culture of other countries, we can say that it belongs to pure Uzbek culture and has a linguistic character. Therefore, in order to deliver the impressionability of the work to a foreigner or a person of another nationality in another Earth of the world, this sentence presented in this work, the translator must find from himself the equivalent corresponding to this statement.

Linguistic loyalty is essential to maintaining the authenticity of the original prose. Translators must balance fidelity to the source language with readability and naturalness in the target language. This balance ensures that the translated works cover the essence and voice of the original author and adapt to the linguistic norms and expectations of the target audience. *“Oq surp yaktak kiygan, mosh guruch soqoli o‘ziga yarashgan go‘rkov yuziga fotiha tortib o‘rnidan turdi:”* This excerpt from “the affairs of the world”, a work attributed to the pen of the Utkir Khoshimov, quotes the word “surp” contained in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language as meaning “Cedar, thread gauze”. “Yaktak "summer light dress, men's jacket," Yaktak" type horse is actually an adjective, with a yak number in Tajik (CF.)” OST“, composed of a tag rave meaning” lower part”; in Tajik, the final g sound alternated to a k sound; meaning "a long summer dress worn by men, sewn alone from thin fabric". From the phrase” rice bearded“, it is known to us that in the Uzbek nation there is an old age, in relation to the enlightened fathers,” mosh rice bearded“, and the phrase means”white bearded, aged somewhere”.

The English translation of this sentence, given in the work of the acute Khoshimov “the affairs of the world”, is given as follows: *“A gravedigger in a long white shirt stands praying aloud”*. So, as we compare this work with the English translation, since there is no equivalent word in English that belongs to the Uzbek culture mentioned above, the translator translated literally and ensured that the reader was understandable in this case. In addition, when we take the sentence “attracted to the face” in the composition of this sentence, this sentence is also a word of pure national character and is rare in other non-Muslim nations. The following definition is given in the passage to the word "Fatiha" in this sentence: 1. *The first, initial Surah of the Quran, the beginning.* 2. *Blessing, applause, which is said to wish goodness to anyone.* 3. *Work - permission, permission, permission, which is given to a person who is starting to perform an action, wishing good luck, happiness. To give the Conqueror. Take the Conqueror.* 4. *After the girl and the young man agree to marry, a ceremony held before the marriage with the aim of informing this to the relatives, the family of the neighborhood; to get engaged.* 5. *In the house where the dead came out, a ceremony is held on the first three days of death, as well as on the days of Eid, in memory of the deceased; bow .*

As we can see, the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language lists various meanings of the word Fatiha. The work gives the meaning of invoking the dead in the face for the purpose of blessing them from behind them.

The translator is assessed based on the level of the translation he has made, with student acceptance playing an important role in assessing his success. The feedback from critics, scholars, and general readers provide valuable insights into how well the translated works resonate with their intended audience. Positive reception is often associated with translations that effectively convey the emotional depth, thematic complexity and harmony of the original Uzbek prose.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that in the history of translation, it will not be an exaggeration to say that the work on the translation carried out to this day and their polished work served as a bridge between peoples and nations on Earth. By translation, a work of art created at one end of the world, or a message of some note, is reflected in a comprehensible way to a person

standing at the other end of the world. So, we can say that this is the value of the created work of art and, in a broad sense, the path that opens up to the use of it by humans. And the fact that people from different countries enjoy one work at the same time testifies to the success of the written work. And in such a painstaking work, the role of direct and indirect translators is endless.

Ultimately, the impact of translations on global literature is beyond linguistic transfer. They are a bridge between cultures and develop mutual understanding and appreciation. By promoting Uzbek literature internationally, translations contribute to a more diverse and interconnected literary landscape.

Thus, a comparative analysis of translations of Uzbek prose works into foreign languages shows the complexity and richness of the translation process. It highlights a variety of strategies for solving linguistic, cultural and literary problems by translators. Through careful study of several translations, this study emphasizes the importance of fidelity to the original text while acknowledging the creative and interpretive choices inherent in translation work.

Continuing research and dialogue among translators, scholars and readers is considered important for the development of the Uzbek field of artistic translation and the development of global literary exchange.

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